

Online interactive map –
Deliverable 2.4

D 2.4 Online Interactive Map of labour market attachment among different vulnerable groups and the mainstream group

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**European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations**

Title: D 2.4 Online Interactive Map of labour market attachment among different vulnerable groups and the mainstream group

Date: October 2025

Responsible organisation: University of Girona

Author(s): Sara Ayllón Gatnau

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Introduction

Building on existing EU and international statistical databases, the interactive map depicts the different labour market attachment realities (e.g., unemployment, underemployment, atypical jobs, earning, working arrangements) between the mainstream and different groups in vulnerable situations, giving a picture of trends across European countries.

The interactive map can be found here on the project's website: [Interactive map - paths2include](https://paths2include.eu/interactive-map/)

The PATHS2INCLUDE project is made up of partners from many European countries, and English is used as the main working language. Hence the original data and indicators of the interactive map are all in English. While we cannot manually translate the Interactive map indicators in all EU languages, we have an automatic translation button which approximately translates the information in your own language, allowing you to capture the main messages.

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